

OBSERVATION AND STUDY OF THE BEHAVIOR OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN THE SOCIAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: Currently, mentally developed, creatively gifted, inquisitive youth are a huge source of forces driving the scientific and technological progress of society, which in the future will have to integrate with the world community in all spheres. In this regard, the search for young talented specialists, their correct orientation, and the formation of knowledge and skills are one of the highest goals.

Keywords: educational efficiency, education, adaptation, social adaptation, innovation, pedagogical skills, personality, socialization.

Today, the trend of development and improvement in all spheres of the world is taking place at a very high pace. This is reflected in the rapid reforms in the field of education in our country. In particular, in order to raise higher education to a new level in terms of quality, the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 and a number of other regulatory documents were adopted.

The success of the ongoing reforms in the social and economic spheres, the development of the country depends on highly educated and qualified specialists. In recent years, the ultimate goal of the fundamental reforms in the higher education system is becoming more and more important as they pursue the same noble aspirations. It should be noted that higher education reforms in our country have risen to the level of state policy, because we understand that the level of higher education determines its future development. In accordance with this policy, issues related to increasing the number of students and higher education institutions, the quality of knowledge, new functions of higher education, the increase in the amount of information, and the wide spread of innovations were resolved.

In order to solve the problems that arose in the higher education system in the short term, clear, consistent and large-scale complex measures were implemented in the following years to fundamentally improve the field, to develop it consistently, to adapt it to the requirements of the 21st century, and to keep up with the times. Also, dozens of important decrees, decisions and programs aimed at the development of the industry were adopted.

Education is a complex process. Only if the student understands the structure of the topic given in the lesson, he can acquire knowledge from the truth. The correct use of the mastered material in assignments is an important indicator of mastering the subject. It is important not only to give new knowledge to students during the lesson, but also to strengthen their learning needs (motivation), work with various sources of knowledge, enable them to plan their actions, provide information about the actions and operations of the cognitive process, it is necessary to learn to gather thoughts, to direct the goal, to be disciplined, to be able to correctly evaluate the achieved result.

"The ongoing educational process in every nation and country is a component of the universal education system. Therefore, like the policy of each country, the education policy should be coordinated based on universal needs. Because the fate of human civilization depends and is equally valuable for all nations" [1].

The Law "On Education" adopted in Uzbekistan and the "National Program of Personnel Training" set new modern requirements for pedagogical personnel. Based on the essence of these requirements, it can be concluded that the level of socialization is an important indicator of future specialists' full activity in their profession. In turn, the nature and aspects of socialization are interpreted in different ways in the scientific literature, that is, the development of society, the impact of this process on the individual, his social adaptation (adaptation), the individual's assimilation of the norms established by society, social adaptation and study of the relationship between socialization and others.

The concept of adaptation (Latin adaptation) was first used in scientific treatment by the German physiologist H. Aubert in the second half of the 19th century (1865) to describe the adaptation of individuals to changes in the external environment. There are many definitions of the phenomenon of adaptation. One of its important aspects is the issue of socialization of the individual. Reciprocity of adaptation and socialization is of great importance in the training of future personnel. The most important thing is to control the assimilation of the norms established by society by young people. This issue is gaining new aspects in the context of globalization. The trend of "human - human" in the past has been replaced by "human - technology" trend today. Today's youth have enormous opportunities for socialization, and therefore the management of the socialization process has become an urgent issue. It is defined as "Adaptation - the adaptation process that occurs in the relationship of living systems with the external environment - a known result of adaptogenesis" [2]. Also, "social adjustment (adaptation) is a type of interaction of an individual or group with the social environment, which is manifested in the process of assimilation of the social environment that is new for the individual or group" [3]. Adaptation is a socio-psychological process, which is a person's ability to successfully carry out his activities in the face of internal and external conflicts, to be satisfied with the results of his activities. Adaptation is a holistic, systematic process that describes the interaction of a person with the natural and social environment.

When it comes to justifying that the social adjustment of students of a higher education institution is an important problem, in this case it is important to reveal the pedagogical interpretation of the concept of "social adjustment".

Socialization is a complex process aimed at the transmission of social norms, principles of behavior and values, its acquisition by a person, which gives an individual the opportunity to express himself as a citizen of a certain society.

Social adaptation is researched as one of the mechanisms of socialization, and overcoming difficulties and problematic situations as a mechanism of mastering a new social experience - student status.

Adaptation is characterized by the acceptance and effective response to the demands placed and expected by the social environment of the students in accordance with the status of the student of the educational institution. In other words, flexible behavior is associated with successful decision-making, initiative, and having clear visions of one's future. Based on this basis, the following can be included in the signs of effective socialization:

1) adaptation in the field of social activity, in this case, achieving general qualification and general professional competence by acquiring personal knowledge, skills and qualifications;

2) adaptability in the field of interpersonal relations, the ability to establish deep emotional ties with other people, etc.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the adaptation of students of higher educational institution to the conditions of the educational institution includes the following aspects:

- the process of social adaptation in students of a higher educational institution has a complex dynamic and requires the mutual harmony of social and personal values;

- in the process of studying at a higher educational institution, the sense of self-awareness of students develops with the help of new tools, the development of the system of valuable relations with the environment and existence continues.

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